

OVERVIEW OF COFFEE GENOME (*Coffea canephora* L.) AND ITS FUNCTION IN STRESS RESPONSE AND CAFFEINE BIOSYNTHESIS

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SUMMARY

Coffea canephora, a coffee species belonging to the Rubiaceae family, is one of the most popular cultivated coffee worldwide. In this study, we overview some important aspects of the genetic genome in *C. canephora* and also review the candidate genes that involve biotic and abiotic stress response and caffeine biosynthesis in the *Coffea* genome. It is reported that the *C. canephora* genome consists of 25,574 protein-coding genes, 2,573 organellar-to-nuclear genome transfers, 6,812 predicted transposable elements (TEs), and 92 microRNA precursors. Coffee-caffeine is synthesized from xanthosine via three methylation steps by NMT genes in *C. canephora* genome: NMT2: cc02_g09350; DXMT: cc01_g00720; XMT: cc09_g06970; MXMT: cc00_g24720; NMT3: cc09_g06960; MTL: cc09_g06950. *C. canephora* genome sequence has recently become a new tool for investigating and analyzing coffee resistance and quality at the molecular level.

Keywords: Caffeine, *C. canephora*, chromosome, miRNA, stress, transposable elements.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are more than 100 species under the *Coffea*, but most coffee bean productions are *C. canephora* and *C. arabica*, with 30% and 70% in total production worldwide (ICO, 2021). Among them, *C. arabica* is preferred to *C. canephora* due to its low-caffeine content and less-bitter taste. It is estimated that an average of 2.25 billion cups of coffee are consumed worldwide, bringing approximately 12 billion US dollars in income each year (ICO, 2021). Therefore, the *Coffea* sp. genome is chosen to sequence, which aids the scientists in deciphering the molecular mechanisms of metabolites biosynthesis pathway and stress response of coffee plant.

There are several published articles about genome sequencing, the coffee transcriptomes, and expressed sequence tags (ESTs) from both robusta and arabica coffee plants (Pallavicini et al., 2004; Vieira et al., 2006). An oligo-based microarray containing 15,721 coffee genes was constructed to analyze potential genes involved in bean maturation, pathogen resistance, and stress responses (Privat et al., 2011). EST sequences of *C. arabica* were recently released (Mishra and Slater 2012).

C. canephora is the diploid species ($2n = 2x = 22$ chromosomes) and is self-incompatible. *C. canephora* reference genome sequence was completed and analyzed in collaboration with Genoscope, IRD, and Cirad (UMRs AGAP,

DIADÉ, and RPB) funded by ANR. Whole genome sequencing strategy for coffee genome sequencing by method following: Illumina GAIIx and Roche/454 GSFLX next generation sequencing platforms were used to generate data. They extracted DNA from coffee leaves. Also, they extracted RNA for transcriptome sequencing. RNA sequences read by Illumina GAII. BWA algorithm technology was used for alignment of RNA reads to produce contigs. *C. canephora* genome was assembled using Solexa/Illumina platform, and GapCloser Software was used for filling Gaps between the contigs. From these data, some specific databases were generated for coffee: Coffee Genome Hub (<http://coffee-genome.org>), an integrated web-based database providing centralized access to coffee community genomics, genetics and breeding data and analysis tools to facilitate basic, translational and applied research in coffee. Data available are the complete genome sequence of *C. canephora* along with gene structure, gene product information, metabolism, gene families, transcriptomics (ESTs, RNA-Seq), genetic markers and genetic maps. The hub also provides tools for easy querying, visualizing, and downloading research data. Also, some information is included in familiar databases, such as NCBI Map Viewer (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/mapview/>). The sequence was published in: "The Coffee Genome Provides Insight into Convergent Evolution of Caffeine Biosynthesis" by Denoeud et al., 2014.

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2. COFFEA CANEPHORA GENOME ASSEMBLY

2.1. Genome sequencing

The genome was sequenced using a whole genome shotgun strategy and was generated using next-generation sequencers (Roche/454 GSFLX and Illumina GAIIx).

In the nucleus genome, there are 13,345 scaffolds with a total length of 586.6 Mb generated from 25,216 contigs (80% of 710 Mb), including 97 Mb (17%) of intercontig gaps. Eighty percent of the assembly is in 635 scaffolds, and the scaffold

N50 (the scaffold size above which 50% of the total length of the sequence assembly can be found) is 1.26 Mb. A high-density genetic map covering 349 scaffolds and comprising around 64% of the assembly (364 Mb) and 86% of the annotated genes was anchored to the 11 *C. canephora* chromosomes (figure 1). More than 96% of the scaffolds larger than 1 Mb were anchored. However, 12,996 scaffolds (totaling 204 Mb) remain unmapped in the current genome release and were grouped arbitrarily into a pseudomolecule named “Un” (unknown), each scaffold being joined by 100 Ns (Denoeud et al., 2014).

Figure 1. *C. canephora* pseudomolecules. Assembled scaffolds were anchored in the 11 linkage groups with the corresponding genetic markers. Lines connect linkage map markers and the DNA pseudomolecule. Oriented scaffolds are represented in blue and non-oriented scaffolds are in green (Adapted from Denoeud et al., 2014).

2.2. Coding gene annotation

To detect conserved proteins and validate the annotation in the *C. canephora* genome, the data were BLASTed against the Arabidopsis (*Arabidopsis thaliana*: TAIR 10; 27,416 proteins), tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*: iTAG2.3, 34,727 proteins) and grape (*Vitis vinifera*: UniProt, 29,836

proteins) proteomes as well as Gentianales proteins contained in UniProt. The numbers in parentheses indicate the number of genes in each cluster, as shown in figure 2 (Denoeud et al., 2014).

Figure 2. Venn diagram showing the distribution of shared gene families among *C. canephora*, *A. thaliana*, *S. lycopersicum* and *V. vinifera* (Adapted from Denoeud et al, 2014).

C. canephora genome is similar to *S. lycopersicum* and *V. vinifera*, and has syntenic relations with other asteroid species (Denoeud et al., 2014).

Protein coding genes in the *C. canephora* genome were automatically annotated using various sources of evidence (cDNAs, RNA-Seq, protein alignments, and ab initio predictions) that were combined into gene models. The result showed that 130,305 coding sequences and 25,574 protein-coding genes were analyzed (table 1). It also has high amount of intron less genes around 5,004, and microRNA precursors are around 92 genes in the genome.

Table 1. The chromosomal genes and their sizes on *C. canephora* genome

Chromosome	Total genes	Size (bp)
Chr 1	2,198	38,193,400
Chr 2	4,000	54,522,928
Chr 3	1,632	32,030,951
Chr 4	1,727	28,191,985
Chr 5	1,661	29,137,935
Chr 6	2,389	37,293,965
Chr 7	2,146	29,833,120
Chr 8	1,718	31,585,744
Chr 9	1,094	22,352,177
Chr 10	1,653	27,624,748
Chr 11	1,753	33,540,656
Chr Unknow	3,603	205,603,396
Total	25,574	569,911,005

(Ptools database: <http://ptools.cirad.fr>).

Note: ChrUn is composed of unanchored contigs.

2.3. Functional annotation and categorization of the coffee genome

All coffee gene models were functionally annotated by assigning their associated generic Gene Ontology (GO) terms and Enzyme codes (EC) through the Blast2GO program (61), based on homology to proteins from other species as determined by BLAST and the occurrence of INTERPRO functional domains identified by INTERPROSCAN. The result showed in figure 3 that classified in three groups (biological process; cellular component and molecular function).

Biological process: Any process specifically pertinent to the functioning of integrated living units: cells, tissues, organs, and organisms. A process is a collection of molecular events with a defined beginning and end.

Cellular component: The part of a cell or its extracellular environment in which a gene product is located. A gene product may be located in one or more parts of a cell. Its location might be as specific as a particular macromolecular complex, a stable and persistent association of macromolecules that function together.

Molecular function: Elemental activities, such as catalysis or binding, describe the actions of a gene product at the molecular level. A given gene product may exhibit one or more molecular functions.

Figure 3. Data Type Summary and GO Analysis Reports: (a) Overview of *C. canephora* genome, (b) Biological process, (c) Cellular component, and (d) Molecular function.

(Coffee-genome hub database: <http://coffee-genome.org>).

2.4. Identification, classification and distribution of Transposable Elements in the *C. canephora* genome

Total of 25,217 contigs was used for self-comparison and classification of the 6,812 predicted transposable elements (TEs) from TEdenovo REPET. Among them, 6,414 fell into class I elements (94%) and a very low number of class II transposons, few MITES, and few SINES, but a huge number of LTR retrotransposons (189 Gypsy-RLG and 388 Copia-RLC) and non-autonomous LTR retrotransposon (RXX, TRIM and LARDS) reference sequences; 1,393 were classified as “chimeric” (elements with more than one TE classification). They also found that 77% of the reference sequences are similar to the TE manual library. Most of them (90%) have identical classification between

both databases. In total, they found that TEs account for half of the coffee pseudomolecules (49.2%). LTR retrotransposons represent 42% of the sequenced genome. Among them, the Ty3-Gypsy family represents the largest part (24.1% of the genome). As observed in other plant genomes and already suggested for coffee (Dereeper et al., 2013), there is an inverse relationship between gene density and repetitive sequences.

2.5. Non-coding gene annotations

Sequences of mature plant miRNAs were retrieved from the Plant MicroRNA Database and used as queries to search the *C. canephora* genome assembly using the LeARN pipeline with default parameters (Noirot et al., 2010).

A list of 92 microRNAs precursors with their predicted hairpinstructures were computationally

predicted from 33 families based on sequence similarity with known miRNAs in PMRD (ahy-miR156b, aly-miR156g, aly-miR156f, vvi-miR156h; acb-miR159, ahy-miR159; aqc-miR160a, csi-miR160, ptc-miR160h; aly-miR162a; aly-miR164a; aly-miR166a; aly-miR167a, ath-miR167m; aly-miR169b, mtr-miR169c, mtr-miR169f; ace-miR170a, aly-miR170; ghr-miR171, aqc-miR171a, aly-miR171b, sbi-miR171f, vvimiR171b; vvi-miR172b, vun-miR172, pppd-miR172b, gma-miR172c, aqcmiR172b; aly-miR390a; bdi-miR393a; ahy-miR394; aly-miR395d, bdi-miR395a; gcl-miR396a, aly-miR396b, aly-miR396a, ghr-miR396a; aly-miR397a; aly-miR398a, aqc-miR398b; aqc-miR399, aly-miR399a, aly-miR399d, bdi-miR399b, bdimiR399b; ppt-miR408b; ppt-miR529d; hpr-miR1120; aly-miR2111a; ath-miRf10005-akr; ath-miRf10239-akr; ptc-miRf10258-akr; ptc-miRf10421-akr; ptc-miRf10467-akr; ath-miRf10574-akr; ptc-miRf10982-akr; ptc-miRf11151-akr; osa-miRf11215-akr; ptc-miRf12256-akr). As their identifications were based on the sequence homology with other plants, the miRNA population size in *C. canephora* is likely underestimated (acb: *Arabidopsis cebennensis*; ace: *Allium cepa*; Ahy: *Arachis hypogaea*; Aly: *Arabidopsis lyrata*; aqc: *Aquilegia coerulea*; ath: *Arabidopsis thaliana*; bdi: *Brachypodium distachyon*; csi: *Citrus sinensis*; ghr: *Gossypium hirsutum*; gma: *Glycine max*; hpr: *Henrardia persica*; mtr: *Medicago truncatula*; osa: *oryza sativa*; pppd: *Populus trichocarpa* x *Populus deltoides*; ptc: *Populus trichocarpa*; sbi: *Sorghum bicolor*; vun: *Vigna unguiculata*; vvi: *Vitis vinifera*) (Denoëud et al, 2014).

miRNA families identified in *Coffea* are deeply conserved among plant phyla. According to the phylogenetic classification by Cuperus et al., 2011, eight families were already present in the common ancestor of embryophytes, one in tracheophytes, two in spermatophytes, and 21 in the angiosperms. Only miR2111 was found to be specific to the eudicots (Denoëud et al., 2014).

3. MOLECULAR FUNCTIONS OF SOME COFFEA GENES

3.1. Abiotic response genes in coffee

The previous studies have documented that the DREB-like gene plays a role as abiotic stress regulators found under cold, heat, low relative humidity, high abscisic acid and light stresses in *C. arabica* and water deficit in *C. canephora*

(Torres et al., 2019). Indeed, CaERF017 was expressed under low temperatures and relative humidity in *C. arabica*, while CaERF053 and CaERF014 were up-regulated under low humidity and high temperatures, respectively. However, the expression of CcDREB1B, CcRAP2.4, CcERF027, CcDREB1D, and CcTINY genes were detected in *C. canephora* under water limitation. Consistently, CcERF016, CcRAP2.4 and CcDREB2F genes also showed overexpression under water limitation in the drought-susceptible line, *C. canephora* clone 22 (Torres et al., 2019). The DREB1D promoter haplotypes (HP15, HP16, and HP17) was identified as tolerance element against abiotic stress, such as cold and water deficit in *C. arabica* involved in ABA-dependent and ABA-independent networks (Alves et al., 2017). The full-length *C. arabica* Protein Domain (CaBDP) gene sequence was extracted from the RNA of drought-tolerant *C. arabica* leaves. Genes have been cloned in Arabidopsis to characterize plant drought and salt tolerance (Nguyen et al., 2016; Nguyen & Hunseung, 2017). Metallothioneine gene expression studies, including *CaMT4*, *CaMT15*, *CaMT3* and *CaMT8* were completed in *C. arabica* by nutrient solution treatment with high copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn) content. The main aim of this investigation was to elucidate the role of metallothioneine in maintaining Cu and Zn homeostasis and in detoxifying these excess nutrients (Bulgarelli et al., 2016).

3.2. Biotic response genes in Coffea

The WRKY1 (CaWRKY1) gene in *C. arabica* is a positive control gene that showed tolerance against abiotic and biotic stress (Rust fungus *Hemileia vastatrix*). Beside, α -amylase inhibitor-1 gene (α -AI1) was able to protect the coffee plants from coffee berry borer insect-pest by *Hypothenemus hampei* (Barbosa et al., 2010; Erika et al., 2015). Up to date, a number of genes for tolerance to biological stresses in coffee have been discovered. Accordingly, the CaNPR1 gene plays an important role in resistance against coffee leaf rust caused by *H. growatrix* in *C. arabica*. This *Nonexpressor of Pathogenesis-Related Gene* (NPR1) has been homologously expressed in other plants (Cavallari et al., 2013), and its role in tolerance to biotic and abiotic stresses was demonstrated in many crops (Silva et al., 2018). Several genes in coffee involve in response to biotic stress, such as GAPDH (SGN-U 347734, SGN-U 356404, 60S RPL7 and

SGN-U351477), ADH (SGN-U 350348), UBQ (SGN-U 347154), while Actin 7 has a role in resistance against *H. anticatrix* (Cavallari et al., 2009; Joseph et al., 2018). Some reference genes are present in the coffee plant tissue, expression studies were performed from *C. arabica* (12 genes) and from *C. canephora* (8 genes). These genes are ubiquitin (UBQ), the medium subunit of Clathrin-conjugated protein (AP47), 60S Ribosomal Protein L39 (RPL39), Elongation Factor 1 α (EF1 α), Alcohol Dehydrogenase Type III (ADH2), β -actin (ACT), Glyceraldehyde 3-Phosphate Dehydrogenase (GAPDH), Ribosome protein 24S (24S), UBQ10, β -tubulin (TUB), Photosystem I P700 Chlorophyll a Apo Protein A2 (PSAB), Caffeine Synthase (DXMT), MDH And Protein Phosphatase 2A (PP2A) (Fernandes - Brum et al., 2017). Cavallari et al. (2009) demonstrated that several internal control genes are useful for expression studies in *C. arabica* under different test conditions. Those genes are Ribosomal Protein 60S L7 (RPL7), ADH, 14-3-3, Poly Ubiquitin, β -actin and Glyceraldehyde-3-Phosphate Dehydrogenase.

Nonspecific lipid-transfer protein (nsLTP) sequences were isolated from *C. arabica* and *C. canephora* and cloned into tobacco lines for functional characterization and genomic analysis

(Cotta et al., 2014).

To date, several transgenic coffee plants have been developed to overcome abiotic and biotic stresses. The number of altered in the coffee plant is described above. In addition, the number of genes, activators, and promoters genes in coffee plants is continuously being discovered to elucidate their function in an adverse environment.

3.3. Caffeine biosynthesis genes in Coffea

Caffeine (1,3,7-trimethylxanthine) is one of the important components of plant-derived drinks, especially in coffee, where it influences the sensorial and physiological impacts of the beverage (Perrois et al., 2015; Zhou et al., 2020). Caffeine is well-known purine alkaloids in several types of eudicot plants, including coffee, cacao, and tea. In coffee, caffeine is synthesized in coffee leaves, which have insecticidal properties, and fruits and seeds, which inhibit seed germination of competing species (Denoeud et al., 2014). Caffeine is synthesized from xanthosine via three methylation steps, involving the successive action of three NMTs: xanthosine methyltransferase (XMT), theobromine synthase [7-methylxanthine methyltransferase (MXMT)], and caffeine synthase [3,7-dimethylxanthine methyltransferase (DXMT)]. SAM, S-adenosylmethionine; SAH, Sadenosylhomocysteine (figure 3).

Figure 4. The principal caffeine biosynthetic pathway (adapted from Denoeud et al., 2014)

Several authors have studied at the molecular level to clarify the regulative mechanisms of caffeine biosynthesis in the Coffea species. McCarthy et al. (2007) have analyzed the XMT and DXMT N-methyltransferases from *C. canephora*. Later on, the study of Denoeud et al. (2014) gained knowledge that is helpful for us to understand insight into the convergent evolution of caffeine biosynthesis with the participation of a series of genes such as CcXMT, CcMXMT, CcMTL, CcDXMT, etc... Perrois et al. (2015) demonstrated that the differential regulation of caffeine modulation content depends on the transcriptional activity monitoring differential expression patterns for the XMT1 and DXMT genes involved in caffeine metabolism in *C.*

arabica and *C. canephora*. Table 2 shows three genes encoding N-methyltransferase amplified in the doubled haploid *C. canephora*, including CcXMT1, CcMXMT1, and CcDXMT. Six genes were amplified in the haploid *C. arabica*: CaXMT1, CaXMT2, CaMXMT1, CaMXMT2, CaDXMT1, and CaDXMT2. On the other hand, Raharimalala et al. (2021) reported very interesting results that the absence of the caffeine synthase gene is involved in the naturally decaffeinated status of *Coffea humblotiana*, a wild species from Comoro archipelago. The result showed that the evolution of NMT genes in *C. canephora* (NMT2: cc02_g09350; DXMT: cc01_g00720; XMT: cc09_g06970; MXMT: cc00_g24720;

NMT3: cc09_g06960; MTL: cc09_g06950), that represented the methylation steps of the caffeine biosynthesis.

Table 2. Identification of the genes encoding the N-methyltransferase involved in caffeine synthesis in *C. arabica* and *C. canephora* species

Species	Gene name	GenBank (NCBI)
<i>C. canephora</i> DH-200-94	CcXMT1	JX978509
	CcMXMT1	JX978507
	CcDXMT	JX978506
<i>C. arabica</i> ET39-DH3	CaXMT1	JX978514
	CaXMT2	JX978515
	CaMXMT1	JX978511
	CaMXMT2	JX978512
	CaDXMT1	JX978510
	CaDXMT2	KJ577792

(Adapted from Perrois et al., 2015)

4. CONCLUSION

Total 25,574 protein-coding genes, 2,573

organellar-to-nuclear genome transfers, 6,812 predicted transposable elements, and 92 microRNA precursors in *C. canephora* genome.

The number of genes that have been altered in the coffee plant is described above such as CcDREB1B, CcRAP2.4, CcERF027, CcDREB1D, CcTINY, CcERF016, CcRAP2.4, CcDREB2F, GAPDH, ADH, UBQ. Also the number of genes, activators, and promoters genes in coffee plants is continuously being discovered to elucidate their function in an adverse environment.

Coffee-caffeine is synthesized from xanthosine via three methylation steps by NMT genes in *C. canephora* genome: cc02_g09350 (NMT2); cc01_g00720 (DXMT); cc09_g06970 (XMT); cc00_g24720 (MXMT); cc09_g06960 (NMT3); cc09_g06950 (MTL). Identification of the genes associated with the caffeine biosynthetic pathway in coffee provided the molecular tool for regulating the caffeine biosynthesis to effectively help coffee breeding and possibly produce more caffeine contents and caffeine-free coffee for consumers in the future.

TỔNG QUAN VỀ BỘ GENE CÀ PHÊ VỎI (*Coffea canephora* L.) VÀ CHỨC NĂNG GENE LIÊN QUAN ĐẾN ĐÁP ỨNG STRESS VÀ SINH TỔNG HỢP CAFFEINE

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TÓM TẮT

Cà phê vối (*Coffea canephora*) thuộc họ Rubiaceae, là giống cà phê được trồng phổ biến trên thế giới. Trong nghiên cứu này, chúng tôi tóm tắt tổng quát những khía cạnh quan trọng về bộ gen cà phê vối, đồng thời tổng hợp những nghiên cứu gần đây về chức năng của các gen liên quan đến khả năng đáp ứng stress sinh học và phi sinh học, các gen tham gia quá trình sinh tổng hợp caffeine. Kết quả cho thấy bộ gen trong nhân của tế bào cà phê vối chứa tổng số 25.574 gen mã hóa protein, trong đó có 2.573 gen mã hóa protein định vị tại các bào quan, 6.812 gene liên quan đến nhân tố chuyển “transposable elements-TEs”, và 92 gen mã hóa tiền microRNA. Hợp chất caffeine trong cà phê vối được tổng hợp từ xanthosine thông qua quá trình methyl hóa và được điều khiển bởi các gen NMT: NMT2 (cc02_g09350); DXMT (cc01_g00720); XMT (cc09_g06970); MXMT (cc00_g24720); NMT3 (cc09_g06960); MTL (cc09_g06950). Những công trình công bố gần đây về trình tự nucleotid và những dự đoán về chức năng gen trong bộ gene cà phê vối đang là nguồn tài liệu rất quan trọng để các nhà khoa học phân tích và chứng minh chức năng của hệ gene nhằm ứng dụng vào chọn lọc và cải tiến chất lượng nguồn giống cà phê vối hiện nay.

Từ khóa: Caffein, *C. canephora*, miRNA, stress, transposable elements.

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